

Yalantosh Bahadir - Skillful Commander and Statesman

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Abstract:

In this article, we will talk about Yalangtosh Bahadir, who is considered a major historical figure and creator of the Middle Ages. We tried to cover all the social and political events of this period using a number of historical sources and researches.

Keywords: Yalangtash Bahadir, historical process, military sphere, Movarounnahr, Ashtarkhanids, internal struggle

Yalangtosh Bahadir was born in 1576 (in other sources, 1578) in the family of the governor of Nurota, and was the son of Boyhojibi, one of the leaders of the Celchin clan [1]. According to his contemporary Mahmud bin Wali's work "Bahr al-asrar fi manoqib al-ahyor", the emir's original name was Khatai Bahadir, and Yalangtosh was his nickname. In history, this breed was mentioned with names such as Yalangtosh ibn Boykhajibi, Yusuf Yalangtosh, Abdukarimbi, Nizamiddin. "Nalyngtosh" (in the meaning of a bare-chested, open-breasted hero) got this name from his pir as a warrior who did not cover his chest with a shield or helmet during battles. At that time, his father Boyhojibi and Khoja Hashimi Dahbedi (the grandsons of Makhdumi Azam) joined hands, became murids and entered his education. Later, Piri Khoja Hashim sent him to the service of Dinmuhammad Khan to improve his military skills. Since Baykhojibi was in the service of the palace during the time of the Shaibani Khans, his son Yalangtoshbi also grew up in the service of the representatives of the ruling house. Yalangtosh Bahadir first fell in the eyes of Bukhara Khan Abdulla Khan II and studied at a special military school under his patronage in 1590-1593. In 1593-1595, he worked as a district head in Bulungur, Loyish and Kattakorgan for his meritorious services to the state.

From his youth, Yalangtoshbi Bahadir grew up to be brave, proud, possessing a sharp mind and intelligence, and deeply mastered military art. A brave, powerful warrior who was not afraid of

anything was regarded as a hero, and all these qualities were characteristic of the skillful general Yalangtosh. In Mahmud ibn Wali's work "Bahr ul-asrar fi manaqibi ul-ahrar" ("The sea of secrets about the glory of noble people"), he is described as a "brave visionary, knowledgeable amir"[2]. According to our opinion, Yalangtosh Bahadir, who spent his youth in Movarounnahr, first studied at the Bukhara madrasa and is fluent in Arabic and Persian. Then, in 1595-1598, he studied in Baghdad[3]. Later, a complex historical situation in Central Asia, that is, the decline of the Shaibani state, the result of the struggle between groups fighting for power, caused the emergence of a new - Ashtarkhanid dynasty. As a result, young Yalangtoshbi was given an opportunity to prove himself as a loyal servant of this dynasty. In short, historical changes brought a creative person to the stage of history. From the age of 19, he was taken under the patronage of Bukhara Khan Dinmuhammad. About this, in the work "Bahr ul-asrar" by Mahmud ibn Wali, "a brave visionary, a knowledgeable amir; He came from the ulus of the Olchin tribe; real name is Khatoy Baha. During the reign of Dinmuhammad Khan, he came from Azaq region of Sagnaq and entered his service; it is said that one of his close people was behind his efforts" [4].

Later, due to his bravery and loyalty, he won the trust of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty. During this period, as a result of studying at a special military school, he learns military and administrative work well, and this will greatly help him in future administration and military operations. During the reign of Bukhara Khan Baqi Muhammad Khan (1601-1605), Yalangtoshbi contributed to the consolidation of the borders of the country and the development of the administrative system as an adviser to the ruler.

After the death of Baqi Muhammad Khan in 1605, his brother Wali Muhammad Khan (1605-1609) took over the throne. Cases of disobedience to the khan's authority have been observed due to the escalation of the internal struggle. Especially since the military-political and economically important Khurasan region was considered the main region where the interests of Bukhara and the Iranian states collided, the leadership in these regions was getting stronger. An army led by Yalangtoshbi was sent to Khurasan, and this area was changing hands between the Ashtarkhanids and the Savafis[5].

At the beginning of the 17th century, the struggle for the throne between the representatives of the Ashtarkhanids in the Bukhara Khanate escalated. On one side of this struggle were Bukhara Khan Wali Muhammad (1606-1611), who was losing control of the state, and on the other side, there were emirs who supported Nadir Muhammad Khan (1642-1645) and Imam Qulikhan (1611-1642), whose political position was increasing day by day. Acad about it. B. Akhmedov analyzes the historical data presented in the work "Bahr al-asror" more widely. Accordingly, in the course of mutual struggle, in 1611, among the amirs, Nadirbek, Bek's son, Muhammad Baqi Kalmaq and Khoja Hashim, along with Yalangtosh Bahadir and his army, were transferred to the side of Imamkuli Khan by Wali Muhammad Khan. goes

It is written about this in the work "Bahr ul Asrar" by Mahmud ibn Wali: "The emirs of Samarkand, Yalangtoshbi otaliq olchin, Muhammad Baqi kalmaq, Nadirbek Shukurbi Saray and others supported Imam Qulikhan" [6].

This decision of the amirs with great military power brought victory for Imam Quli Khan in the political struggle. So, Wali Muhammad Khan, who was short-handed, had no choice but to flee to Iran through Chorjoi with his family and several emirs. At the end of February 1611, a number of emirs and religious leaders put Imam Qulikhan on a white blanket and made him Khan. Yalangtosh Bahadur, who was among these influential emirs, had a great influence. In that year, Nadir Muhammad Khan was appointed to rule Balkh region. So, Yalangtosh Bahadur, who has a large military force, left the service of Wali Muhammad Khan, which caused his failure, and his fighting on the side of Imam Quli Khan served for his accession to the throne.

It is known that the next political processes took place with the active participation of Yalangtosh Bahadur. For example, the former ruler Vali Mohammad, who fled to Iran to Shah Abbas, asks the Shah for help to regain the throne of Bukhara. In response, Shah Abbas mobilized 80,000 of his military units to fight against Wali Muhammad Khan's Imam Qulikhan[7]. When the young and inexperienced Imam Qulikhan, who was frightened by the news that the Iranian army was coming to Bukhara, failed, he planned to flee to Balkh and settled in Karshi. In this situation, Yalangtosh Bahadir again entered the main political scene and took control of the situation in Samarkand. Together with Shukurbi Sarai, he calls on all emirs and scholars to support Imam Qulikhan in the fight against Iran. Yalangtosh Bahadir brings Imamqulikhan from Karshi to Samarkand. They start a joint action to repel the attack of the common enemy[8].

Here, Yalangtosh Bahadir appears as a skilled politician who was able to unite not only all emirs, religious people, and even the ruler in the fight against the common enemy. In addition, these evidences indicate that he has the ability to make quick and correct decisions when the peace of the country is in danger.

Thus, when Yalangtosh Bahadir and Imamguli Khan started the defense work together, the Iranian army stopped at Zarman district near Samarkand city. Due to the unequal power, Imamquli Khan, Yalangtosh Bahadir and other influential emirs ask for help from the Kazakh Khans Abulay Sultan and Ishim Sultan. Both Kazakh sultans, who came to help, sent their small number of soldiers to help Samarkand, and with their main soldiers began to plunder the villages of the city of Movarounnahr. It is interesting that Vali Muhammad Khan also requested military assistance from the Kazakh sultans.

It is clear from the course of events that with the help of Imamkuli Khan Yalangtosh Bahadir and other emirs, he will win over both enemies - Kazakhs and Iranian Redheads: Abulai Sultan will return to Turkestan after claiming the villages and regions around Samarkand. However, Imamkuli Khan was forced to consult with Yalangtosh Bahadir and Shukurbi Saray again in order to eliminate the threat of Sultan Ishim, who was still in Miyanqal. With their advice, Ishim gave the sultan Tashkent, Turkestan and the surrounding lands and managed to eliminate the threat of the Kazakhs. It can be understood from these events that the rulers often counted on the opinion of Yalangtosh Bahadir in the tense situations that arose in the state during the struggle with external enemies. The era of Imam Quli Khan, who led the policy of centralization, is considered the most developed and strengthened stage during the reign of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty in the Bukhara Khanate. In 1612, Imamkulikhan, who took into account his contribution to the acquisition of state administration, loyal and exemplary services, appointed Yalangtosh Bahadir as the governor of Samarkand region. The support of his elder Khoja Hashim is also considered important in getting the position of mayor.

Barefoot Bahadur will later be appointed to the role of father. In the Middle Ages, fatherhood was one of the highest positions, he was equal to the father of the ruler and controlled the distribution of water in the Bukhara Khanate. The border of this distribution was from Samarkand to Karakol, and mainly Samarkand and its districts were required to distribute water fairly, from high-ranking officials to ordinary people. Also, this position corresponded to the status of the prime minister, and people from the Uzbek clan were appointed to it.

The political influence of Yalangtosh Bahadir, who participated in the battles for the territories of the Khanate at the same time as Imam Quli Khan, who ruled for more than thirty years, increases in the state administration. In this regard, he made a significant contribution to the expeditions organized to Khurasan to strengthen the southern territories of the Ashtarkhanids. At this time, the issue of Rustam Sultan, the son of Vali Muhammad Khan, another historical person who was an obstacle to the political stability of the Ashtarkhanid state in Movarounnahr and Balkh, cannot be resolved without the participation of Yalangtosh Bahadir. Acad. B. Ahmedov gives the following

information based on the work "Bahr al-asrar". Former ruler Vali Muhammad Khan fled to Iran, leaving his son Rustam Sultan in Marv. He also settled in Ubeh and Shafelon regions in return for Iran's support, and between 1612-1622 and 1631, he frequently attacked the regions of Balkh, Seyston, Farah, Shibirghan, Andhuy, and Chechektu, disturbing the peace of the country. Nadir Mohammad Khan Rustam sent a large army under the leadership of Yalantosh Bahadur against him in 1623, after the diplomatic relations he established several times with Iran to solve the problem of Sultan Rustam did not bring any benefit. Rustam Sultan again fled to Iran, and as a result, until 1631, the Ashtarkhani Khans were free of problems related to him. But in 1631, Sultan Rustam again attacked the southwestern regions of Balkh. This time, Yalangtosh Bahadur is the leader of decisive military forces sent against him. This time he besieged the forces of Sultan Rustam in the Meruchak fortress and thus managed to solve the problem. So, on the condition that Rustam Sultan pays tribute to Balkh, a peace agreement is concluded between the two sides, and the siege is lifted.

In conclusion, it can be said that the internal political problems related to Valimuhammad Khan and his son Rustam Sultan in the Ashtarkhanid state, as well as the foreign policy issues related to the Iranian state, were solved by the active action of Yalangtosh Bahadur. Yalangtosh Bahadurkhan also took an active part in the military campaigns of Bukhara khans to conquer Tashkent and Turkestan. In particular, Suhail's work "Imamkulinoma" contains information about how Yalangtoshbi fought against the Kazakh sultans Tursun Sultan and Abulay Sultan in constant battles for neighboring territories and tried to save the territories he had won.

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